

IMPACT OF THE NUMERICAL MODEL ASSUMPTIONS ON THE WATER DIFFUSION KINETICS OF A UD COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The composite materials with thermosetting matrices and reinforced by glass fibres have high initial thermomechanical characteristics. The enhancement of these composite structures is closely linked to a better understanding of their behaviour during hydrothermal ageing. Indeed, the degradation of fibre/matrix interface/interphase in humid environment is often responsible for the fall in mechanical properties. This paper deals with the impact of the numerical models assumptions on the diffusion kinetics of a unidirectional composite. Numerical results are compared with experimental values obtained from microthermal analysis (μ -TA).

In the initial state, μ -TA measurements show an increase of the matrix molecular mobility at decreasing distance from fibres surface. It defines a "Thermal" interphase with a low crosslink density up to 4 μ m width around each monofilament. Different diffusion kinetics must then be considered inside the matrix. A finite element analysis is proposed to study the impact of the interphase area around each fibre. Many assumptions are simulated to identify their influences on the final results. The diffusion parameters used in the finite element models of the composite give results consistent with experimental and analytical values. Moreover, the numerical models show the high influence of fibre distribution on water diffusion kinetic and the "barrier effect" for the high rate of fibres.

A more realistic model defined from optical microscopy picture is in agreement with the experimental results.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composites used in aeronautical industry have generally high mechanical properties at initial stage. Under service, due to the mechanical, thermal or/and environmental stresses, these properties will be decreased more or less quickly. The ageing process in humid environments is due to complex interaction between physical and chemical effects. The drop in mechanical properties usually observed can be the result of degradations at matrix/reinforcement interface or interphase [1,2]. The study of this specific area is limited by means and scales of analysis, but it was recently investigated at sub-micron scale [3,4]. Different techniques show an interphase stiffness lower than the matrix stiffness. For thermosetting matrix reinforced by glass fibres or glass beads, the matrix network seems to be highly modified over several micrometers around each monofilament due to an incomplete curing [5–7] or to plasticizing effects from fibre treatment [8–12]. A molecular mobility different from the bulk matrix one can be characteristic of the presence of interphase. These modified areas will be influenced water diffusion and solubility inside the composite material.

Many authors have studied the water diffusion through epoxy resins [13–18]. The results show that the coefficient of diffusion is directly dependant from some parameters as temperature, resin composition, curing agent... Moreover, the presence of fillers modifies the water absorption behaviour, depending on the properties of this filler (adhesion resin-filler) [15]. From these studies, many different values of diffusion coefficient are proposed for the epoxy resin. In many cases, the water diffusion kinetics can be well described by a Fick law [16–20] especially at short times. A deviation from this model can be observed at long times, a Langmuir-type model will be more appropriate [13,14]. Many authors have studied water diffusion phenomena by a finite element approach. The diffusion behaviour generally present in the finite element code is based on Fick model.

Fick has been inspired by Fourier and Ohm and the analogy between diffusion and conduction of heat or electricity [21]. Fine results are obtained for different materials [22–24]. For the others, such as epoxy / glass fiber composite, this model can be discussed even it is usually used in the studies [25–27]. Few authors have proposed to perform the Fick model or to write in finite element software a new diffusion law. Loh et al. describe the non-fikian epoxy water uptake as two parallel fikian models with two different diffusion coefficients and saturation levels [28]. LaPlante et al. [29] use Prony series, introduced by Weitzman [30] and Roy [31], to modify the coefficient and boundary conditions as dependant of time in Fick model.

The aim of this study is to show the impact of the numerical model assumptions on the water diffusion kinetics applied to an unidirectional composite. Results from different numerical models will be compared to experimental values from microthermal analysis.

2 MATERIALS AND METHOD

2.1 Composite materials

The thermosetting matrix is a DGEBA-based epoxy resin (Araldite® LY556 from Ciba-Geigy) with aliphatic polyamine (XB3486 from Huntsman) selected as hardener at 33 parts by weight of resin. This resin has a long pot life compatible with the filament winding process at ambient temperature used to obtain laminas. E-glass fibres (300 Tex, 14 μm) have been treated with a commercial sizing. The unidirectional composites obtained are reinforced with 50% vol. glass fibres (Figure 1). The porosity resulting from filament winding process remained lower than 1% vol. for a fibre content of 50% vol. Epoxy resin plates (without fibres) were also moulded following the curing cycles recommended by the manufacturer.

Figure 1: Unidirectional composite with 50% vol. glass fibres (optical microscope).

2.2 Micro-Thermal Analysis (μ -TA)

Micro-thermal analysis has been used to characterize microstructure of the composite and get information on the interphase size and properties. This technique combines the visualisation and positioning methods of atomic force microscopy (AFM) with the technology of thermal analysis with a calibrated thermo-resistive probe [32]. A scan in apparent thermal conductivity of a few square micrometers can thus be obtained, which gives the glass fibres distribution inside the composite (Figure 2a). Specific locations are then chosen on this scan to perform the micro thermal analysis in order to follow the gradient of thermal properties existing from fibre towards bulk matrix. The experiment consists in following the deflection in sensor position associated to the glass transition during a heating ramp from ambient temperature to 250°C at 10°C/s. A change in slope ($d\Delta z/dT$) corresponds to a softening temperature T_s associated to the glass transition of the polymer (Figure 2b). A μ TA 2990 from TA Instruments micro-thermal analyser was used. The thermal affected zone is estimated about 1 μm diameter [33].

Figure 2: Example of localized thermal analysis measurements (1-6) with apparent thermal conductivity image obtained on UD (a) and softening temperature evolution at increasing distance from monofilaments (b)

2.3 Hydrothermal ageing test

Normalized composite and resin plates (75x75x2 mm³) were immersed at 70°C in deionized water up to saturation (between 8 and 16 weeks) according to aerospace standard [34]. The water uptake is measured regularly on a precision Ohaus balance (+/- 0.5 mg) during ageing and the water absorption is then reported as a function of time or square root of time.

$$M(t)(\%) = \frac{m(t) - m(0)}{m(0)} \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

with $m(0)$ et $m(t)$ sample mass at the initial state and at the time t .

3 FICK ANALYTICAL MODEL

In first approximation, a Fickien kinetic can be used:

$$\frac{M_t}{M_s} = 1 - \left[\frac{8}{\pi^2} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n+1)^2} \exp\left(-\frac{D(2n+1)^2\pi^2 t}{4h^2}\right) \right] \quad (2)$$

with M_t water mass absorbed at the time t , M_s saturated water mass, D diffusion coefficient and h plate thickness.

At short time, this equation can be simplified to describe the linear part and to give the diffusion coefficient D :

$$\frac{M_t}{M_s} = \frac{2}{h} \sqrt{\frac{Dt}{\pi}} \quad (3)$$

Absorption curve (mass concentration vs square time) for epoxy resin obtained by experimental measurement has permitted to calculate the diffusion coefficient D (Figure 4).

Figure 3: Experimental and Fick model of the curve of epoxy-resin absorption.

Indeed, D value can be directly calculated from the gradient a of the curve linear part:

$$a = \frac{\Delta M_{\infty}}{M_0} \cdot \frac{4}{h} \sqrt{\frac{D}{\pi}} \quad (4)$$

The diffusion coefficient of the epoxy-resin is $15.10 \cdot 10^{-13} \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$. This value will also be used in finite element model for the composite matrix.

Fick analytical model	Resin	Composite
D ($\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$)	15×10^{-13}	7.75×10^{-13}
Ms (%)	2.29	0.60

Table 1: Diffusion parameters identification from Fick analytical models.

3 FINITE ELEMENT MODELS

A 2D finite element model has been realized in the commercial software AbaqusTM to simulate the water diffusion along specimens. Due to symmetries, only half thickness has been used for simulation. A boundary condition has been applied at the edge of symmetry. Water immersion has been modelled by boundary condition (Figure 4).

Figure 4: modelling of water diffusion in UD composite.

Properties used in the numerical models have been reported in the Table 2. Arbitrary value have been chosen for the glass fiber in agree with the assumption than glass fiber has none water uptake in the range time considering in this work. To describe the interphase area, many values will be proposed from literature or from inverse method.

	Matrix epoxy	Glass fiber
D (m ² .s ⁻¹)	15x10 ^{-13*}	1x10 ^{-30**}
Ms (%)	2.29*	1x10 ^{-30**}

* Experimental value

** Arbitrary values which traduced none water uptake in the range time considering

Table 2: Properties materials used in numerical model.

Linear quadrilateral element (DC2D4) and linear triangular elements (DC2D3) have been used respectively for epoxy-resin and composite models. In a same meshing, all elements have the same surface to minimize the calculi error of the arithmetic average.

First of all, mass concentration results have been obtained by the average at each node. So mesh elements must have the same surface all over the sample. In a previous study, the influence of the size of element has been shown [35]. For resin sample models, elements size has not affected the mass concentration results. So an edge element of 5.10-2 mm will be used. However, for composite models the elements size has a large effect on mass concentration calculated which can be explained by the edge effect phenomena at the matrix/fibre interface. Indeed, a gradient in mass concentration is present at each interface in the first fibre element due to nodes continuity conditions (Figure 5). The converged solution has been obtained with the mesh element size lower than 1.5 µm.

Figure 5: Illustration of the edge effect phenomena at the matrix/fibre interface (mass concentration calculated from two different meshes).

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Local measurement results

As shown by several authors [3-12], the introduction of glass fibre modifies the matrix properties, which will influence the water uptake behaviour. In order to characterize this matrix around fibres, local thermo-mechanical measurements have been performed by µTA. The softening temperature T_s , which is associated to the glass transition temperature of the polymer network, is reported for each LTA measurements vs distance from monofilament (Figure 6). The results show a decrease of the softening temperature when the distance from fibres surface decreases. Different T_s measurements on bulk resin have also been performed and superimposed for comparison in a grey area. The interphase region is then defined by the area where the softening temperature is lower than the softening temperature of the bulk. In that case the interphase is nearly 10 µm width and the softening temperature is highly decreased compared to the resin one. This phenomenon can be attributed to incomplete curing

[5-7] or plasticizing effects from fibre treatment [8-12]. The dispersion of results is explained by heterogeneities of cross-link density and by heterogeneous sizing distribution on fibres. These results confirm that the resin properties are strongly modified by fibres introduction. Moreover, a plasticized or under crosslinked network will probably change the diffusion kinetics compared to the one of bulk resin network. The modelling of composite and resin water uptake should confirm these assumptions.

Figure 5: T_g evolution vs. distance from monofilament for epoxy/glass fibre composite with bulk resin T_g measurements in grey area as resin reference [36].

4.2 Impact of glass fiber distribution

Many fibre arrangement models have been proposed in order to quantify their impact on water diffusion (Figure 6). All models have been calculated with the same elements size and same fibre fraction (50% in volume). The model 1 describes a perfect fibre arrangement ($r = 7 \mu\text{m}$) with a length of $20\mu\text{m}$ between two fibre centres. The Model 2 and Model 3 have an alternated arrangement with a gap of $10 \mu\text{m}$ in vertical direction and a lower distance between two consecutive vertical line of fibres. The Model 4 has a random fibre arrangement where no fibres are in contact. The Model 5 is similar to the Model 4 with one barrier effect due to contact between some fibres. The Model 6 has a periodic arrangement with confinement matrix areas in the centre of each pattern. The Model 7 has a periodic arrangement of fibres which generate many barrier effects. And, the last model, Model 8, proposes a periodic arrangement of fibres where contact fibres generate barrier effects and confinement matrix area.

Fibre arrangement has a significant impact on mass diffusion results (Figure 7). A barrier effect due to fibre proximity has been clearly shown. Three different behaviour can be identified depending on fibre arrangement:

- o Periodic arrangement with large gap between fibres (Model 1 to Model 2);
- o Periodic or random arrangement with lower gap between fibres (Model 3 to Model 4);
- o Barrier effect with contact fibre (Model 5 to Model 8).

The only difference between the Model 4 and the Model 5 is that 4 fibres have been placed in contact with 5 previous fibres in order to simulate a barrier effect. The results show that the absorption curve decreases down to 10% with only one fibre barrier. Moreover, the real UD composite with 50% vol. glass fibres present many fibres in contact with closed resin areas (Figure 1). It suggests that some barrier effects with confinement must be taken into account to model the composite (Model 6). This model actually decreases water uptake at short times but diffusion kinetics is too slow and solubility too high compared to experimental values. Model 6 underestimates closed volumes as suggested by Figure 1. Nevertheless, increasing closed volumes will even decrease the diffusion coefficient which is already too low.

A real fibre distribution, based on optical microscopy observations (Figure 1), will be used in the finite element models for the next of this study. This model takes account of contacts between fibres (Figure 8), which represent a barrier effect to water diffusion [36].

Figure 6: Numerical models with different fibers distribution developed

Figure 7: Numerical immersion composite absorption curve with different models of fibres arrangement

Figure 8: Finite element model of the real fibers distribution defined from optical microscopy observations [36]

4.3 Impact of interphase area

Only one model based on a real fibre distribution has been used to follow the impact of the interphase. The Figure 5 has shown that an interphase area is present around each fibre. The size of this modified matrix area has been measured around $10\ \mu\text{m}$. Due to high rate of fibre (50% vol.) and the size of the interphases, we can assume that all the matrix part can be considered as an interphase. Few authors have studied these interphases and few properties have been reported in the literature. Bond [37] has proposed a value of the water diffusion based from the resin coefficient as described by the equation (4). Whoo and Piggott [38] have shown in case of interphase in the composite, that the diffusion coefficient can be considered as 10 times the $D_{\text{bulk matrix}}$.

$$D_{\text{Interphase}} = 10 \times D_{\text{Resin}} \quad (4)$$

To take into account the interphase in the numerical model, in first approach, all the matrix part has been considered as an interphase and defined by a mean value. The coefficient diffusion of this interphase has been equal to $15 \times 10^{-13}\ \text{m}^2\ \text{s}^{-1}$ in agree with the equation 4. The results of the analytical, experimental and numerical model have been compared in Figure 9. In this case, results are highly lower than experimental values. To fit experimental results with the model, the matrix diffusion coefficient must be increased up to $100 \times 10^{-13}\ \text{m}^2\ \text{s}^{-1}$.

To improve the result, the interphase area can be divided in two parts where the softening temperature is slightly modified (less than 10% of the bulk resin values) and highly modified (more than 10% of the bulk resin values, Figure 5). The properties of the interphase are applied only for the highly modified part of matrix (i.e. size around each fibre equal to $4\ \mu\text{m}$). In first approach, the value proposed by the equation (4) is used for describe the interphase. Numerical results have been compared to experimental values. It can be clearly seen that the shape of the curves is nearly the same than the experimental one but numerical model does not fit the experimental curve. The value used for the coefficient diffusion of interphase $D_{\text{interphase}} = 10 \times D_{\text{resin}}$ can not allow to fit the experimental data (Figure 10). This difference can be explained by the representative elementary volume (REV) used by Bond [37]. Indeed, he proposed a same REV to describe a linear distribution of fibre or a random distribution. Moreover, the REV cannot take into account fibre contacts while the contacts highly modify water diffusion kinetics as previously shown. A new diffusion coefficient is evaluated by the inverse method in the case of a real fibre distribution. Indeed, it fits much better the experimental results than the two others models (Figure 10). Experimental values are well fitted with a value of $D_{\text{interphase}} = 7.2 \times 10^{-12}\ \text{m}^2.\text{s}^{-2}$. So a new ratio is proposed between the matrix and the interphase diffusion coefficient by the equation (5).

$$D_{\text{Interphase}} = 5 \times D_{\text{Resin}} \quad (5)$$

Figure 9: Matrix absorption curve where matrix is considered as an interphase.

Figure 10: Matrix absorption curve with the presence of a more “realistic” interphase area.

9 CONCLUSIONS

Microthermal analysis shows that an interphase of several micrometers width is present around each monofilament. This interphase has a glass transition temperature much lower than the bulk resin one, which is associated to an increase in molecular mobility attributed to an undercrosslinked or plasticized matrix.

From gravimetric measurements in immersion, the water uptake behavior was considered as Fickian in first approximation for both the composite and the resin. Kinetics diffusion parameters were then used in numerical models.

To simulate diffusion phenomenon in composite presenting a high diffusion coefficient mismatch between matrix and reinforcement, a particular attention must be taken to mesh the geometry. Indeed, it has been shown that all elements must have the same surface and that boundary elements (at fibre/matrix interface) must have a size lower than 10% of reinforcement size.

A simplified microstructure cannot be used to model water diffusion in UD composites. The numerical model must be based on a realistic microstructure which presents fibre contacts and a wide matrix/fibre interphase of high molecular mobility and water diffusivity. A matrix diffusion coefficient higher than the bulk resin must be used to fit correctly the experimental data, showing that the matrix is highly modified by the presence of fibres. This is consistent with literature and with the increase in molecular mobility highlighted by μ TA measurements. A new relation between the kinetics coefficient of the matrix and the interphase has been defined in this work where $D_{\text{interphase}} = 5 \times D_{\text{bulk matrix}}$.

The numerical simulation shows that the matrix is strongly modified by the presence of fibres, compared to the resin alone. A matrix diffusion coefficient higher than the bulk resin one must be used to fit correctly the experimental data. This is consistent with the increase in molecular mobility highlighted by μ TA measurements.

A mean value was used to describe the interphase diffusion coefficient. It would now be interesting to correlate the gradient in molecular mobility measured by μ TA to a gradient in diffusion properties inside the interphase to improve our numerical model.

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